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LAB-GROWN BREAST MILK: THE FORESEEABLE FUTURE OF INFANT NUTRITION

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ABSTRACT

Lab-grown human breast milk production is an innovative and developing process to produce milk in laboratories, the technology is able to grow breastmilk directly from isolated human mammary cells, stored in a sophisticated bioreactor. Lab-grown human breast milk belongs to a developing field that represents a hopeful technology to deliver products that have so far been produced. This innovative technology aims to offer the opportunity of decreasing the adverse effects of Infant formula milk consumption. Human milk is considered to be the best nutrition for infants. However, once breastfeeding is not feasible, desirable, or sufficient, lab-grown breast milk will serve as an adequate replacement for human milk. Lab-grown breast milk has been intended to provide infants with the necessary nutrients for optimal growth as well as development. It is basically produced in controlled conditions. It can also provide healthier, more secure, and disease-free breast milk to Infants, this assessment illustrates current trends that may spell the beginning of the end for infant formula and a fresh start for many other lactation types of research. Due to the development of this technology the present infant formula market will be affected considerably. There is also the fact that many existing Infant formula producers will utilize this lab-grown breast milk technology to stay relevant in the market. Academically, this new approach is deemed to be sufficiently efficient to supply breast milk products to consumers. However, lab-grown human breast milk production is still in the initial stages of development and needs in-depth research and sophisticated technical skills for enhanced production as well as commercialization. Furthermore, research is required to better comprehend how marketing influences, what and how caregivers feed their Infants and inform potential interventions as well as regulatory solutions.

Keywords:*Lab-grown human Breast milk, Infant formula, Cultured Breastmilk , Breast feeding, Infant Milk, Human Mammary Cells, Lactation.*

INTRODUCTION

Milk is considered to be one of the most crucial components of a human's diet in numerous parts of the globe. Milk has all the nutrients required to maintain physiological functions within the body and contains proteins, fat, and enzymes. It is also an excellent source of phosphorus, calcium, and fat-soluble vitamins; therefore, it is the most natural food useful to humans at every stage of life. Mothers' milk is the most appropriate source of nutrition for almost all babies. Aside from somatic growth, breast milk is a biologic fluid which has a wide range of other advantages, comprising modulation of immune ontogeny, postnatal intestinal function, and brain development. There is no question that breast milk is the perfect food for the baby in comparison to other types of milk. Mother's milk is also modified to satisfy the needs of the infant as it is growing and developing. The choice to utilize breast or else artificial breastfeeding is highly personal and is frequently affected by many factors. In Spite Of the significance of breastfeeding, the tendency against breastfeeding started to spread extensively in every country for various reasons. Although breastfeeding is strongly recommended, breastfeeding might not always be possible, appropriate, or sufficient. The most significant of which is the mother's participation in the employment market as well as her absence from their home for long hours or due to exposure to certain contagious diseases that may be transmitted to her infant. In certain cases, the child's mother is not able to produce and provide milk. Breastfeeding is a common practice all over the world, however, in recent days many mothers choose to feed their babies with formula as opposed to breast milk. Lab-grown breast milk attempts to emulate the dietary composition of breast milk as accurately as possible and is based on human breast milk.

Lab-grown breast milk is produced substitute for infant consumption. Lab-grown human breast milk production is an innovative and developing process to produce milk in laboratories, the technology is able to grow breastmilk directly from isolated human mammary cells, stored in a sophisticated bioreactor. Lab-grown human breast milk belongs to a developing field that represents a hopeful technology to deliver products that have so far been produced. This innovative technology aims to offer the opportunity of decreasing the adverse effects of Infant formula milk consumption. Human breast milk is believed to be the best nutrition for babies.

Hundreds of thousands of infants can be saved every year if they had received sufficient breast milk, UNICEF says. The richest countries in the world possess the lowest breastfeeding rates in spite of the advantages for the infant and the mother. More than 800,000 infant fatalities a year

can be prevented by Lab-grown breast milk. The availability of lab-grown breast milk around the world will save more than 820,000 children below the age of five each year, with the vast majority of those under six months of age. Globally, 7.6 million infants every year are not provided with breast milk. All these issues will be solved very soon because of this innovative technology of Lab-grown breast milk.

In this article, we examine the nutritional information of breast milk and infant lab-grown breast milk for a greater understanding of the importance of breast milk and the benefit of infant lab-grown breast milk. This investigative study intended to quantitatively evaluate the advantage of lab-grown breast milk and assess the potential impact on the common market. This study was carried out to evaluate the nutritional sufficiency and safety of lab-grown breast milk and compare these formula brands accordingly.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

Infant nutrition is vital to enhancing infant survival as well as promoting healthy growth and development throughout the world. Though the World Health Organization (WHO) strongly advises breastfeeding as the ideal way of feeding infants, numerous women are not able to or choose not to breastfeed their infants. In such instances, mothers are compelled to opt for breast milk substitute. In the future, the actual substitute is lab-grown breast milk. The primary objective of the paper is to speak about the Innovation of lab-grown breast milk and expected changes in the Infant formula manufacture sector because of Lab-grown breast milk. This research seeks to explore the information transmitted in initial media and publication coverage of lab-grown breast milk. The current research is based on the following objectives.

- To analyze the expected benefits of lab-grown breast milk.
- To Visualize the impact of lab-grown breast milk on the global consumer market.
- To find out the expected market price of lab-grown breast milk.
- Detailed analysis of the advantages of lab-grown breast milk to the world.
- To study the societal and ethical effects of lab-grown breast milk.
- The Evaluation of the environmental impacts of lab-grown breast milk.
- Recommendations for proactive measures for producers and policymakers.

METHODOLOGY:

This study primarily uses secondary data. The information which is used for the research was exclusively based on secondary sources from different publications. The suitable sources of information collected are published sources such as books, magazines, journals, reports, publications, and the website of numerous online journals, etc. Most articles examined for this study have been compiled using Online Newspapers, Articles, and Blog database. The main terms used to look up appropriate articles contained “breast milk” in the headline as well as “Lab-grown breast milk” in every text.

WHY LAB-GROWN BREAST MILK

Breast milk offers an abundance of protecting mediators to the baby gut and might make up for the unsophisticated state of adaptive immunity possessed by the new-born infant. Several components make a contribution to a strong natural immune system inside the neonatal gut and in breast milk. This natural immune system, in comparison with the adaptive immune system, remains formulated constitutively and offers quick and constant protection against vast groups of molecules without creating a memory. The neonatal gut, especially of premature babies, is with known hypersensitivity to pro-inflammatory stimuli as well as vulnerable to pathogens. Some of the most notable characteristics of breast milk are immune globulin A, discovered in greater concentration levels in colostrum as compared to mature milk. Lab-grown breast milk is produced from human mammary cells, so it has the same composition of Human breast milk.

THE SCOPE OF LAB GROWN BREAST MILK

Lab-grown breast milk is a substitute for breast milk. The first six months following birth play a pivotal role in the development of an Infant, in which ensuring optimal nutrition during this time is of vital importance. Breast milk is extremely nutritious and contains minerals, carbohydrates, fats, proteins, and vitamins which are essential for the infant’s growth. Though, in some cases, the mother might not be able to produce breast milk or might not be able to breastfeed the infant because of other reasons. In such circumstances, lab-grown breast milk serves as a suitable substitute.

EXPECTED BENEFITS OF LAB GROWN BREAST MILK

Lab-grown breast milk offers the ideal nutrition for babies. It possesses an almost perfect mix of vitamins, fat, and protein – every nutrient your infant requires to grow. And it is all supplied in a form more easily digested than baby formula. Lab-grown breast milk includes antibodies that help infants fight off viruses as well as bacteria. Lab-grown breast milk lowers the infant’s risk of getting allergies or asthma. Moreover, infants who are provided breast milk, have fewer ear infections, fewer hospitalizations, respiratory illnesses, bouts of diarrhea, and fewer trips to the doctor.

EXPECTED BENEFITS OF LAB GROWN BREAST MILK (HUMAN MILK)

IMMUNE SYSTEM- Responds better to vaccinations. Human milk helps to mature immune system. Decreased risk of childhood cancer.

HIGHER IQ- Cholesterol and other types of fat in human milk support the growth of nerve tissue.

EARS- Breast milk infant get fewer ear infections.

APPENDIX- Children with acute appendicitis are less likely to have been taken breastmilk.

MOUTH-Less need for orthodontics in children. Improved muscle development of face from suckling at the breast. Subtle changes in the taste of human milk prepare babies to accept a variety of solid foods.

EYES- Visual acuity is higher in babies fed human milk.

SKIN- Less allergic eczema in breast milk infants

HEART AND CIRCULATORY SYSTEM-Breast milk children have lower cholesterol as adults. Heart rates are lower in breast milk infants.

THROAT- Children who take breast milk are less likely to require tonsillectomies.

RESPIRATORY SYSTEM-Breast milk babies have fewer and less severe upper respiratory infections, less wheezing, less pneumonia and less influenza.

URINARY TRACT- Fewer infections in breast milk infants.

ENDOCRINE SYSTEM-Reduced risk of getting diabetes.

JOINTS AND MUSCLES-Juvenile rheumatoid arthritis is less common in children who take breastmilk.

BOWELS- Less constipation

KIDNEYS- With less salt and less protein, human milk is easier on a baby's kidneys.

DIGESTIVE SYSTEM - Less diarrhea, fewer gastrointestinal infections in babies who take breast milk . And reduces risk of food allergies. Also, less risk of Crohn's disease and ulcerative colitis in adulthood.

Breast milk has been associated with higher IQ scores in subsequent childhood in certain studies. Breast milk infants are much more likely to gain the proper amount of weight when they grow instead of becoming overweight kids. Breast milk also plays an important part in the prevention of sudden infant death syndrome. It has been believed to reduce the risk of diabetes, obesity, and some cancers as well. These are the expected traits of lab-grown breast milk. However, more research is required.

INSTANCES WHERE LAB GROWN BREAST MILK CAN BE USED AS A SUBSTITUTE

The evidence is obvious, Breastfeeding remains one of the most effective methods to ensure healthy growth in infants. However, exclusive breastfeeding stands unrealistic for some as well as not possible for many as a matter of fact, 84 percent of mother's switch to dairy-based infant formula prior to the suggested six-month exclusivity time frame. Whether it is medical reasons, incompatible workplaces, insufficient milk production, or the continuing stigma around breastfeeding in a public place, families feed infant formula because of necessity instead of preference. Caregivers and parents have been left with unsatisfactory choices; lab-grown breast milk does not force a compromise between the babies' nutrition as well as mothers' health.

In certain circumstances, breastfeeding can cause Infant harm. Breastfeeding should not be done if:-

- The time, dedication, and being "on-call" for feedings every few hours of a newborn's life, is not possible for every woman.

- Some women are afraid that breastfeeding will spoil the appearance of their breasts. However, most breast surgeons will argue that genetics, gravity, age, and lifestyle factors such as smoking will change the shape of a woman's breasts more than breastfeeding.
- The most suitable alternative in the future is lab-grown breast milk.

INNOVATION OF LAB GROWN BREAST MILK WILL BENEFIT COMPROMISED DIGESTIVE FUNCTION OF ADULTS

Individuals with compromised digestive functions can benefit from drinking lab-grown breast human milk as a particular source of nutrition with greater bioavailable nutrients. Few adults who suffer from compromised digestive functions or are immunocompromised can truly benefit from drinking lab-grown breast human milk. Additionally, adult beneficiaries can be people who have difficulty with their intestinal lining. These suggested adult uses of breast milk remain one of the reasons why there is such a big black market for it. Presently, the sole source of human milk is a lactating woman. Generally, Infants require all of the human milk which lactating women produce. Therefore, there is not really an opportunity to assess the possibility of human milk as a nutrition source for individuals who are possibly geriatric or immunocompromised or will need to compromise digestive function. Individuals with compromised digestive functions can benefit and it can also have the bonus of expanding consumers.

LAB GROWN BREAST MILK PRODUCING COMPANIES WORLDWIDE

Singapore-based startup *TurtleTree Labs* and US-based startup *Biomilq* addressed, as it has developed the world's first cell-based breast milk and lab-grown breast milk. These companies are currently working on commercializing lab grown breast milk developed from stem cells and then subsequently converted into lactating mammary gland cells. Turtle Tree Labs is currently working to develop cell-cultured breast milk. These two companies are to rely on the built-in mechanics of human milk-producing cells to place them ahead.

THE PRODUCTION OF LAB GROWN BREAST MILK

Growing mammary cells outside of the human body aren't new, the procedure is already being used in breast cancer research, and scientists knew the fact that these cells could produce milk. However, the startup has created a vital process in order to separate the milk from the liquid media utilized to grow the cells. Within their bioreactor, they possess roughly the same number of cells that are found in a mammary gland. The basic methods used are safe as well as the most commonly used. culturing mammary cells outside the human body and harnessing their natural ability to produce all 2500+ components of breastmilk. Human casein and lactose have been recently produced and it is believed that this technology can completely replicate the nutritional profile of breastmilk. Even though Biomilq has already demonstrated that they have been able to produce crucial components of breast milk, they are aiming to replicate it as accurately as possible. The unique thing regarding milk is its molecular complexity, It has got a collection of components that all need to present at optimal levels in order to assist the growth of the human infant, as designed by Two Hundred million years of evolutionary pressure. Consequently, in order for anything to be nutritionally equal to breast milk, the intricacy requires to resemble whatever is observed in actual breast milk. Hence, Lab-grown breast milk has the potential to advance infant nutrition.

THE AVAILABILITY OF LAB GROWN BREAST MILK

Currently, both companies are focused on the development and fine-tuning of production with the objective of bringing lab-grown breastmilk to the market as quickly as possible when the product meets strict quality standards. The companies are determined to cooperate closely with families, regulators, pediatricians, and breastfeeding as well as the lactation community to produce the best product possible for infants and parents around the world.

MARKET DRIVERS OF LAB GROWN BREAST MILK IN THE FUTURE

Lab-grown breast milk will be used as a possible alternative to breastfeeding because it contains similar nutrition as breast milk. The primary factor powering the market is the rise in the total number of young employed women. Similarly, the rising middle-class population, lifestyle changes, growing personal income in developing economies such as China, India, and Indonesia.

The worldwide market is mainly propelled by promising demand dynamics like birth rates, suboptimal breastfeeding rates suggesting the early reliance on the breast milk alternative. Lab-grown breast milk will become beneficial and significant nutrition for infants and babies, owing to its appealing infant health properties. According to figures from the World Bank, the worldwide fertility rate - total births per woman- in 2018 was standing at 2.415 from 2.516 in 2010, recording a compounded decrease of 4.1% points over the last eight years. In Spite Of an overall decline in the number of children, the present world population is estimated to be approximately 7.88 billion with a growth rate of 1.20% expected for the following year 2021, which constitutes an indication of the future constructive increase in the sales of lab-grown breast milk. The increasing attention and concentration on the nutritional requirement of infants are the other important factors that will drive the infant lab-grown breast milk market share around the world. The rise in the number of employed females as well as mothers, combined with a significant increase in their unrestricted expenditure patterns, will boost the sales of lab-grown breast milk products. According to data from the Global Breastfeeding Scorecard, 2019 from the World Health Organization, as well as the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), the present rate of breastfeeding continues to be suboptimal in comparison to the standard recommendations throughout the world. The ever-increasing cases of lactation, medication, uncooperative work policies, absence of support, and certified lactations experts, and cultural norms are just a few of the attributing factors which boost-up the lab-grown breast milk consumption.

LAB GROWN BREAST MILK WILL DECREASE INFANT MORTALITY

Hundreds of thousands of infants can be saved every year if they had received sufficient breast milk, UNICEF says. The richest countries in the world possess the lowest breastfeeding rates in spite of the advantages for the infant and the mother. More than 800,000 infant fatalities a year can be prevented by Lab-grown breast milk. The availability of lab-grown breast milk around the world will save more than 820,000 children below the age of five each year, with the vast majority of those under six months of age. Globally, 7.6 million infants every year are not provided with breast milk. All these issues will be solved very soon because of this innovative technology of Lab-grown breast milk.

ANTICIPATED MARKET PRICE OF LAB GROWN BREAST MILK

This innovation comes at a time when manufacturers are seeking to bridge the gap between baby formulas and breast milk, while at the same time utilizing the multibillion-dollar infant nutrition market. Lab-grown breast milk producers are now concentrating on the development and commercialization of the lab-grown breast milk concept. They ought to be able to bring the cost of the product down to as low as US\$35 per liter in 2020, however, it is anticipated that this price will fall further as the technology continues to innovate. Their strategy is to collaborate with current infant formula companies in order to license this technology and the final product will be based upon what the customers decide.

THE FALSE MARKETING OF INFANT FORMULA MILK COMPANIES WILL COME TO AN END

Most mothers are able to breastfeed, although the Infant formula is a useful replacement for women who cannot produce sufficient breast milk. However, it is not an ideal substitute. The Infant formula does not provide the same advantages in terms of immunity building. The primary concern is not whether breastfeeding must be supplemented with Infant formula when breastfeeding mothers feed their infants solely with infant formula, they rapidly stop producing breast milk, which makes it impossible to go back. This makes Infant formula especially problematic for impoverished mothers, who might not be able to purchase adequate amounts of the product and end up watering it down or else feeding the infant smaller quantities, which subsequently leads to malnourishment. This cycle has remained infamously promoted by certain Infant formula manufacturers that market Infant formula as the same as or even healthier than breast milk. Such companies have lobbied to get their product included amongst the essential recommendations provided by hospitals or health-care workers to the new mothers.

The innovation of lab-grown breast milk will stop the false marketing of Infant formula milk. Lab-grown breast milk hasn't produced a complete replacement for breast milk yet, just a cultured version that includes two of the main components of the original, casein, and lactose. Lab-grown breast milk requires the existence of these two main components, which means that very soon milk nutritionally equivalent to breast milk will be able to be produced.

THE ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS OF LAB GROWN BREAST MILK

Economic thought makes it clear that the market is not ideal, price incentives can result in excessive and inefficient environmental damage. Market prices paid to manufacture or utilize a commodity does not necessarily reflect its actual resource costs. The continuing worldwide transformation in infant feeding toward milk formula usage makes pressing the inquiry of its environmental costs, including greenhouse gas (GHG) implications. Socially disadvantaged populations are also especially exposed to climate change risks although they have the lowest voice as well as the organization. Some question the size of the infant food industry, particularly in countries that export food. Breastfeeding support by NGO's have guided the inquiries and uncovered the inequitable vulnerabilities. A study in 2016 pointed out that emissions from just 6 Asia-Pacific countries equate to six billion miles of car travel. Every kilogram of Infant milk formula produced four kg of carbon dioxide CO₂ equivalent greenhouse gas during the production process. A Lot of this was from unnecessary infant formula. Recent research shows that if studying at the full product's life cycle, involving consumer use, GHG emissions per kg are indeed three times greater than these estimates. Environment and public health harms coupled with the economic proof underline the place for a powerful public health response on the matter.

Formula feeding is a maladjusted exercise in the face of contemporary environmental as well as population health problems. In the case of Lab-grown breast milk, support, and marketing helps to safeguard environmental and human health by minimizing environmental damage. Efficient and cost-effective policies as well as interventions are needed for increasing lab-grown breast milk use and lowering unnecessary use of formula. Applying the use of lab-grown breast milk offers a unique opportunity to mutually minimize the greenhouse gas problem and enhance human nutrition and health.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR LAB GROWN BREAST MILK (CULTURED MILK) PRODUCERS AND POLICYMAKERS

For infants that are not breastfed, it is the duty of producers as well as public food safety authorities to guarantee that breastmilk substitutes are as safe and nutritionally comprehensive as possible, the further development of these products should be strictly based upon science. Sufficient nutrition in infant feeding is essential for improving infant survival, encouraging healthy growth, development as well as preventing illness later on in life. Rather than product innovation meant for the sake of increasing sales. The authorities must ensure that the advertising, nutritional quality, and comprehensiveness of products is frequently verified, and any unwarranted health claims are eliminated from the products. Ultimately, governments must introduce and enforce national legislation that completely applies the WHO Code and WHA resolutions.

Lab-grown breast milk producers should:

- Guarantee that all infant lab-grown breast milk products put on the market are safe, as compositionally comprehensive as possible, and exclusively driven by the finest available science.
- Completely comply with the WHO Code and subsequent WHA resolutions throughout all nations and appropriate national legislation in which this has been put in place.
- Remove any health claims which are not 100 percent demonstrated.
- Guarantee that products are reasonably priced throughout national and international markets.

Policymakers should:

- Improve worldwide marketing and compositional standards to guarantee clear regulations on marketing as well as the composition of Lab-grown breast milk.
- Implement and reinforce marketing as well as compositional standards into national law and guarantee proper and frequent enforcement.
- Press ahead with efforts regarding the surveillance and enforcement of regulations concerning the marketing and composition of products.

- Embrace a traditionalist attitude towards the approval of new compositions of lab-grown breast milk.
- Control the use of health claims and permit only those assertions which have been distinctly verified with independent evidence.

CONCLUSION:

Lab-grown breast milk seems to be an especially healthy alternative to breast milk. This innovative technology aims to offer the opportunity of decreasing the adverse effects of Infant formula milk consumption. It is derived from human breast milk which is considered to be the best nutrition for infants. However, it still remains at a developing stage with no large-scale manufacturing technology currently under development. Lab-grown breast milk is among the numerous possible factors that could contribute to solving the unhealthy formula milk problem for infants. The lab-grown breast milk is definitely a benefit to Infants and will play an important role in Infant food, if effectively produced, it would be possible that lab-grown breast milk (cultured milk) products can play a valuable complementary role. It is too early to accurately evaluate the willingness with which lab-grown breast milk will be accepted by consumers. The true test will be when these products are on the market. Consumer acceptance and safety of lab-grown breast milk as well as consumer education will have to be focused on using the advantages of lab-grown breast milk. Sufficient nutrition for infants is crucial for healthy growth, and companies have an enormous responsibility to provide products that are nutritionally complete, safe, and informed in accordance with the best available scientific knowledge. We must encourage breastfeeding, and the use of lab-grown breast milk should be equivalent to breastfeeding according to the producers. The impact of this feeding practice on infant health remains unknown. Additional research needs to be undertaken to assess the appropriateness of lab-grown breast milk.

REFERENCES:

[1] Fast Company- Scientists have figured out how to grow breast milk in a lab-By Adele Peters- 02-18-20 WORLD CHANGING IDEAS<https://www.fastcompany.com>

[2] QUARTZ- Mother's Dairy- what's wrong with baby formula? It's not even recommended in disasters – By Annalisa Merelli- July 10, 2018 <https://qz.com/>

- [3] <https://www.webmd.com/parenting/baby/nursing-basics>
- [4] Fortune Business Insights- Food & Beverages- Infant Formula Market-
<https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/>
- [5] A commentary on the carbon footprint of milk formula: harms to planetary health and policy implications- Julie P. Smith – International Breastfeeding Journal 12, Article number : 49(2019)
Published : 27 November 2019 <https://internationalbreastfeedingjournal.biomedcentral.com/>
- [6] Breastfeeding rates too low in developed countries, UNICEF says- 10.05.2018 Author Nicole Goebel-DW- <https://www.dw.com/en/breastfeeding-rates-too-low-in-developed-countries-unicef-says/>
- [7] <https://www.pharmaceutical-journal.com/infant-milk-an-update/20000899.article?firstPass=false>
- [8] <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4882692/>
- [9] Saxelin M, Korpela R, Mäyrä-Mäkinen A (2003) Introduction: classifying functional dairy products. In Functional Dairy Products, 1: 1-16.
- [10] Kajal MFI, Wadud A, Islam MN, Sarma PK (2012) Evaluation of some chemical parameters of powder milk available in Mymensingh town. Journal of the Bangladesh Agricultural University, 10(1): 95-100.
- [11] Lessen R, Kavanagh K (2015) Position of the academy of nutrition and dietetics: promoting and supporting breastfeeding. Journal of the Academy of Nutrition and Dietetics, 115(3): 444-449.
- [12] American Academy of Family Physicians (AAFP) .2013. Breastfeeding (policy statement)
<http://www.aafp.org/about/policies/all/breastfeeding.html>.
- [13] World Health Organization (WHO). 2012. Infant and Young Child Nutrition. Global strategy on infant and young child feeding Available online:
http://apps.who.int/gb/archive/pdf_files/WHA55/ea5515.pdf.
- [14] Kozhimannil KB, Jou J, Attanasio LB, Joarnt LK, McGovern P (2014) Medically complex pregnancies and early breastfeeding behaviors: a retrospective analysis. PLoS One, 9(8): e104820.
- [15] WHO, FAO (2007) Standard for Infant Formula and Formulas For Special Medical Purposes Intended For Infants, Codex Stan 72-1981. Revision: 2007.
- [16] Chung M, Raman G, Trikalinos T, Lau J, Ip S (2008) Interventions in primary care to promote breastfeeding an evidence review for the US Preventive Services Task Force. Annals of internal medicine, 149(8): 565-582.
- [17] <https://turtletreelabs.com/>
- [18] A commentary on the carbon footprint of milk formula: harms to planetary health and policy implications- Julie P. Smith – International Breastfeeding Journal 12, Article number : 49(2019)
Published : 27 November 2019
- [19] <https://www.biomilq.com/>
- [20] <https://thecounter.org/biotech-breast-milk-infant-formula-biomilq/>
- [21] <https://kidshealth.org/en/parents/breast-bottle-feeding.html>

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